

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 3 |
March 2022 | Monthly Journal by
TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly peer reviewed Journal by **The
World Association of Scientists &
Professionals**

Analysis on the Transition Zone of Deformation in Sheet & Plate Bending Processes While Using FEA

Khan Muhammad Idrees^{1*}, Xi Chen²

¹Department of Aerospace Engineering, Shenyang Aerospace University, China

²Department of Computer Science and Technology, Dalian University of Foreign Languages, China

Accepted March 20, 2022

Published March 25, 2022

Copyright: © The Author(s); Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

*Corresponding Author: Khan Muhammad Idrees

Funding: None

How to cite this article: Khan Muhammad Idrees, Xi Chen (2022). Analysis on the Transition Zone of Deformation in Sheet & Plate Bending Processes While Using FEA. *North American Academic Research*, 5(3), 152-163. doi:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6383187>

ABSTRACT

The aim of the paper is to research the variation laws of transition zone of V-shape bending in sheet and plate. According to the previous theory, the bending sheet is divided into two parts, deformation area which is distorted by punch loading, and non-deformation area where the rest of the specimen is undistorted, but we always ignore that the deformation area cannot transform into non-deformation area. We consider that there is no distortion in non-deformation area, while there is distortion with high value in the deformation area in the width direction. The transition area, which appears between deformation area and non-deformation area, is discussed in this paper. Distortion occurs in transition area and its value does not keep constant neither change with high values, it changes slowly and with very small values. Here I explore the position, interval and distortion value of transition area of bending sheet & plate by finite element analysis. When I simulate the process of narrow sheet & plate bending, the Finite Element software ANSYS is employed.

As for the simulation, I use aluminum alloy 7075-0 in the V-shape bending simulation, and I label all the transition area of all the workpieces after the simulation with the help of nodal displacement measurement. Then I select several workpieces as a group and divide them into five layers and measure the distortion values on each layer in the transition zone. Therefore, I can conclude the variation laws of width of transition area from the inner layer to outer layer bases on these values. After all the simulations, a comprehensive analysis was performed with the help of various initial widths and punch radii to compare different width changes in the transition area.

本文的目的是研究厚板V形件弯曲过渡区的变化规律。根据此前的传统理论，弯曲后的板料分为两部分，即在凸模成形力作用下有畸变产生的变形区，以及不发生畸变的非变形区。但是传统理论忽略了变形区并不能直接突变为非变形区。本文提出，在变形区和非变形区之间存在一个区域，此区域的存在畸变且畸变量逐渐变化，这

个区域被称为过渡区，本文就是要关注这个过渡区。在过渡区内有形状畸变现象，畸变程度不大且变化缓慢。文中采用有限元分析和弯曲工艺试验的方法对过渡区的位置、范围及其畸变量进行了探索。基于理论推导和一些基本假设得出了变形区以及过渡区的应力应变值。利用有限元分析软件 ANSYS 对窄板弯曲过程进行模拟。观察有限元模拟后的板料畸变情况并记录相关数据。

测试方面，我们在室温下的V形弯曲模拟中使用铝合金7075-0，并借助节点位移测量对模拟后所有工件的所有过渡区域进行了标记。然后我们选择几个工件为一组，将它们分成五层并测量每一层的畸变值。因此，我们可以根据这些值得出内层到外层过渡区宽度的变化规律。在所有模拟之后，借助各种初始宽度和冲压半径进行综合分析，以比较过渡区域的不同宽度变化。

Keywords

Transition Zone, Narrow & Wide Sheet & Plate Bending, Shape Distortion, Ansys, Aluminium alloy 7075-0

Introduction

The bending deformation, as an important plastic forming technology, is widely used in industrial production. The curved pieces with various shapes are in the fields of aerospace, automotive and so on. The precision of the curve's pieces will influence the production costs and production efficiency directly, and then it will impact the manufacturing efficiency. However, many problems occur during the sheet bending process, such as cracking and distortion and so on. Therefore, systematic analysis on deformation law of sheet bending has impact on improving the production efficiency and manufacturing standard (1).

However, there are many deficiencies in the current literature on the research of bending. One of them is that there are too many assumptions and simplifies on the research of complex bending models and avoid the exploration on the core problems, therefore the results are difficult to convince people.

And another one is that there are discussions in detail about the wrinkling, cracking and spring back during the sheet metal bending process, but we ignore the basic research. And the research is focused on wide sheet but has few researches on narrow sheet. But narrow sheets are widely used in industrial practice as well. Therefore, alongside the wide sheet, the research on narrow sheet is also very meaningful.

In the actual bending process, the bending results are quite different when the width sizes of sheet are various. We call the sheet with relative width $b > 3t$ wide sheet and that with relative width $b < 3t$ narrow sheet, where b is the width of sheet and t is the thickness of sheet. When the wide sheet bends, due to the restraints in the width direction, the width dimension and cross-sectional shape do not substantially change while there is change in thickness and length of sheet. When the narrow sheet bends, there is no restriction in width direction which can be considered as a free state. So, the stress is zero in width direction and there is significant change in cross section. As the material can flow freely, hence there is compression in width direction and thickness direction of the material under the tangential tension on outer layer fiber. As for the inner layer of sheet, the compression on tangential fiber will cause extension in width direction and thickness direction so that the cross section is no longer a rectangle and turns into a sector (2). The movement of stress and strain

neutral layer, decrease in thickness of sheet (3), distortion in width direction and transition zone and its influence factors have important impact on research of narrow sheet bending law and bending programs during the narrow sheet bending process. But up to now there is no detailed research on narrow sheet bending transition zone and need further exploration and analysis. In this paper I will introduce narrow sheet bending transition zone and its influence factors based on this.

The Main Content of the Research

In the traditional analysis of sheet bending deformation, the bent sheets are divided into two areas, i.e., deformation zone and non-deformation zone. And we think that the elastic and plastic forming only happen in deformation zone, and the deformation amounts of the materials on same level with different central angle positions are same, they do not change when the central angle change. There is no deformation in non-deformation zone. There is a mutation on the position of curved line segments in the deformation zone and arc tangent to the non-deformation zone. Therefore, the size distribution will have step-mutation in the critical surface from deformation zone to non-deformation zone, causing the material discontinuity here. This is a significant contradiction to the basic assumption that the nodes should be continuous after material deformation and the actual situation, hence it is a mistake. Therefore, I divide the bending sheet into three areas here which are deformation zone, transition zone and non-deformation zone, shown in Fig. 1. And I consider the transition zone is where the distortion happens.

Fig. 1 The deformation zone, transition zone and non-deformation zone of the bending narrow sheet

Distortion of Sheet & Plate Bending in the Width Direction

The narrow sheet with relative width less than 3, there is no constrain on elongation and compression in width direction and materials can flow freely. When bending deformation occurs, there is tangential tension on outer fiber layer, so that the width of sheet decreases. And there is tangential pressure on inner fiber layer causing the elongation of materials in width direction. The difference in material deformation on inner and outer layer causes the shape change of cross-section, from rectangle to sector. This is called distortion phenomenon of sheet bending (5). The amount of distortion on material cross-section is related to many factors such as initial width, bending radius, the position of chosen layer and position of cross-section. In the study of material distortion, it is almost based on the traditional theories, which divides the bending sheet into deformation zone and non-deformation zone. The deduced result is quite different from the experimental results. In this topic, I divide the bending sheet into three zones, which are deformation zone, transition zone and non-deformation zone and I think the distortion amount is continuous, which means the distortion amounts

on the same layer in deformation zone are same. The distortion amount decreases in transition zone and reaches zero in non-deformation zone. The width of the sheet does not change.

Sheet & Plate Bending Simulation

The finite-element analysis software ANSYS was used for the bending simulation process. First ANSYS was started. During the simulation, aluminum alloy 7075-0 was introduced for the material model. Mechanical properties of AA 7075-0 is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of AA 7075-0

Density	Tensile Yield Strength	Tensile Ultimate Strength	Thermal Conductivity	Resistivity
2.8e-006 (kg mm ⁻³)	104.9 (Mpa)	224.7 (Mpa)	0.134 (W mm ⁻¹ C ⁻¹)	(5.099e-005 ohm mm)

The narrow sheet & plate of aluminum alloy 7075-0 had the following dimensions: Length x thickness x width = 150 x 8 x 8 mm. The punch radius was 15mm, and the bend angle was 90. Explicit Dynamics and Multilinear Isotropic Hardening was assigned. Other dimensions are given in the Table 2.

Table 2 Specimens dimensions

Thickness (mm)	Width (mm)	Punch radius (mm)	Other parameters
2	2	2,5,8	Material 7075-0 L=150 (mm), bend angle=90°
	5	2,5,8	
	8	2,5,8	
5	5	5,10,15	
	15	5,10,15	
	30	5,10,15	
8	8	8,15,20	
	20	8,15,20	
	40	8,15,20	

The geometry was created in Solidworks and imported to the ANSYS. After making the geometry, meshing was done. Body sizing was provided according to the thickness of the aluminum plate & sheet varying from element size of 0.5mm to 3.5mm. The elements of the radial face of the punch were also sized from 3 to 5 mm. The default size was used elsewhere at 10 mm with a default growth factor of 1.2. The contacts were then defined. Frictionless contacts were used between the punch and the sheet, and between the sheet and the die. Frictionless support was defined for the faces of the punch. The base of the die was made as fixed support. The stainless steel material model was applied to the punch and die. The load was applied at the top surface of the punch acting vertically downward, and the simulation was then started.

Sheet & plate Bending Simulation Results

By ANSYS sheet metal bending process of post-processing, you can directly see the bent sheet deformation in all directions, the stress and strain. Fig. 2 shows sheet & plate bending deformation results.

Observe the narrow metal plate distortion during the bending process, namely in the width direction, the inner fibers exhibit elongation phenomenon, The outer layer of the fibers exhibits shrinkage. And from the

center to the ends of the sheet, there is a certain distortion in the width direction Law

(a) Plate

(b) Sheet

Fig. 2 Sheet & Plate bending results

Curved narrow plate bending distortion mainly reflected the changed widths of the narrow sheet, and therefore here the focus of concern is Z direction of displacement, stress and strain, shown in Fig.3

(a) Strain top view

(b) Strain bottom view

(c) Strain section view

Fig. 3 Cross sectional strain in the Z and X direction

The outer edge of the curved sheet is taken a plurality of nodes as shown in Fig. 3 (a), the display position of each node shift amount. The displacement amount is gradually reduced until it is close to zero. This area is the above-mentioned transition area, the displacement amount is gradually reduced and also a curved transition area.

Fig. 4 Narrow sheet side Z-direction displacement

Fig. 4 is a side view of the Z-direction displacement in the angular position θ theoretical analysis to select five nodes, they correspond to the theoretical analysis of the five positions A, B, C, D, E, which were measured the displacement of several nodes, and each node to calculate the position of the sheet width.

Determination of the Transition Zone of Sheet & Plate

This research focuses on the law of distortion of the transition zone, so the accuracy of the position of transition zone is important. The method of marking transition zone of each specimen is substantially the same. Here I explain with the specimen Thickness x Width x Punch radius=2-2-2, Thickness x Width x Punch radius=5-5-5 and Thickness x Width x Punch radius=8-8-15

As the sheet bending is symmetric about the center of curvature, therefore I only need to mark the transition zone of one side of the sheet. First, I measure the initial widths of the three specimens and record. Then I draw 11 nodes of directional deformation in Z-direction with constant distance 1mm and 2.54mm between each 2 consecutive nodes on the sheet side from the bending center. Shown in Fig. 4. Measure the outer layer width of each node, and record the measured results and initial widths in Table 3. Please note that all the dimensions are given in millimeters throughout the paper.

Fig. 4 Schematic nodes

Table 3 Specimen width at different locations

	Specimen Thickness x Width x Punch radius=2-2-2	Specimen Thickness x Width x Punch radius=5-5- 5	Specimen Thickness x Width x Punch radius=8-40-20
Initial Width	2	5	40
Position1	1.69	3.99	37.39
2	1.76	4.24	38.05
3	1.87	4.63	38.28
4	1.93	4.82	38.5
5	1.95	4.88	38.81
6	1.96	4.92	39.25
7	1.97	4.95	39.74
8	1.97	4.96	39.92

9	1.98	4.98	39.95
10	1.98	4.98	39.96
11	1.98	4.99	39.97

As can be seen from Table 3, for Specimen Thickness x Width x Punch radius=5-5-5, the sheet & plate widths increasing briefly and width difference between nodes are at least 0.5mm at node 1 to node 6 and increased slowly with very small intervals from node 7 and it is around initial width and keeps stable node 11. So the transition zone is the area between node 7 to 11, mark the transition zone.

And we can determine the transition zone for specimens Thickness x Width x Punch radius=2-2-2 and Thickness x Width x Punch radius=8-40-20 with the same method. Shown in Fig. 4.

Distortion Measured Transition Zone of Sheet & Plate

1. Explore the distortion law of transition zone at different layers of sheet. Test conditions:

Thickness x Width x Punch radius=8-8-8, Thickness x Width x Punch radius=8-20-8 and Thickness x Width x Punch radius=8-40-8 as work piece number 1,2 and 3. Divide the specimen into five layers in thickness direction and mark as nodes location A, B, C, D, E. And mark the positions of three sectional transition area in the transition zone, as position 1, position 2 and position 3. (See Fig. 5) Measure the width of 5 layers on the three positions and record the measured results in Table 4.

Fig. 5 Sheet stratified and transitional zone location

Table 4 Width changes at different locations plate & sheet at different levels in the transition zone

zone	number	Initial width	A	Δw_A	B	Δw_B	C	Δw_C	D	Δw_D	E	Δw_E
	1	8	7.938	-0.062	7.959	-0.041	7.994	-0.006	8.026	+0.026	8.059	+0.059
1	2	20	19.895	-0.105	19.926	-0.074	19.989	-0.011	20.103	+0.103	20.198	+0.198
	3	40	39.848	-0.152	39.88	-0.12	39.981	-0.019	40.079	+0.079	40.175	+0.175

	Average			-0.106		-0.078		-0.012		+0.069		+0.144
	1	8	7.971	-0.029	7.982	-0.018	7.997	-0.003	8.010	+0.01	8.023	+0.023
2	2	20	19.927	-0.073	19.956	-0.044	19.995	-0.005	20.036	+0.036	20.077	+0.077
	3	40	9.943	-0.057	39.955	-0.045	39.992	-0.008	40.033	+0.033	40.073	+0.073
	Average			-0.053		-0.036		-0.005		+0.026		+0.058
	1	8	7.986	-0.014	7.992	-0.008	7.998	-0.002	8.002	+0.002	8.007	+0.007
3	2	20	19.954	-0.046	19.973	-0.027	19.995	-0.005	20.010	+0.01	20.028	+0.028
	3	40	39.962	-0.038	39.976	-0.024	39.993	-0.007	40.010	+0.01	40.025	+0.025
	Average			-0.033		-0.019		-0.005		+0.007		+0.02

As it can be seen from the table, the amount of distortion decreases first and then increases from layer A to layer E, which is from outer layer to inner layer of bending sheet, in transition zone. In the outer layer, distortion amount is negative which means the sheet is narrowed. However, the distortion amount is positive in the most inner layer, which means the sheet is widened. The distortion amount is close to zero near layer C and D, means the location of strain neutral layer exist between these two layers. Layer D is in the area which is close to the most inner layer of the bending sheet, so there is significant inner shift in the strain neutral layer. We can draw the coordinates of distortion amount at different positions in different layers. Shown as Fig. 6

Fig. 6 distortion amounts at different positions in different layers

In the figure above, 1,2,3,4,5 are correspond to layers A,B,C,D,E. Among the three curves, position 1 has biggest change while position 3 has smallest change. Therefore, in the transition zone, the distortion amount

is biggest near deformation zone and decreases gradually when it moves to both ends. The distortion amount is nearly zero near the non-deformation zone.

2. Explore the impact of width of narrow sheet & plate to transition zone. I take three specimens per sample from Table 2: Thickness x Width x Punch radius=8-8-8, Thickness x Width x Punch radius=8-20-8 and Thickness x Width x Punch radius=8-40-8. Mark the transition zone and three different positions 1,2,3 in transition zone. Measure the most outer layer of the sheets, which is the change amount of width of layer A in Fig. 5. Record the average values of results in Table 5.

Table 5 Distortion amount of transition zone under different initial width conditions

	Initial width	Zone1	$\Delta w1$	Zone 2	$\Delta w2$	Zone3	$\Delta w3$
W=8	8	7.96	-0.04	7.97	-0.03	7.99	-0.01
W=20	20	19.94	-0.06	19.95	-0.05	19.97	-0.03
W=40	40	39.92	-0.08	39.94	-0.06	39.96	-0.04

Draw distortion value of the three locations with varying widths in chart shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 The impact of sheet & plate width distortion amount in transition zone

Fig. 7 shows that sheet & plate width will have an impact on the distortion of transition zone, the impact of sheet width is shown by the impact of relative width b/t.

3. Explore the impact of curvature radius to transition zone. We take three specimens per sample Thickness x Width x Punch radius=8-8-8, Thickness x Width x Punch radius=8-8-15 and Thickness x Width x Punch radius=8-8-20. Mark the transition zone and three different positions 1,2,3 in transition zone. Measure the widths in outer layer of the sheets in position 1,2,3. Record the results in Table 6.

Table 6 Amount of distortion of transition zone under different bending radius

	Initial width	Zone1	$\Delta w1$	Zone 2	$\Delta w2$	Zone3	$\Delta w3$
R=1	8	7.91	-0.09	7.92	-0.08	7.93	-0.07
R=2	8	7.94	-0.06	7.95	-0.05	7.96	-0.04
R=3	8	7.97	-0.03	7.98	-0.02	7.99	-0.01

Draw the result of Table 5 in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 Effect of distortion of narrow sheet bending radius in the transition zone

Overall, with the bending radius increases, the amount of distortion of the transition zone also decreased. In addition, the curvature radius changes, the position of transition zone will change as well.

Conclusions

Narrow metal sheet will produce distortion in bending process, and the distortion amounts are different from the curvature center to the ends of the sheet. Near the center of the sheet, there is a layer with large distortion amounts and they are same. This layer is called deformation zone. There is a range with distortion amount being 0 far away from the bending center, it is non-deformation zone. Between the deformation zone and non-deformation zone is transition zone, in which the distortion amount changes gradually. I discussed the changing law in transition zone of aluminum narrow sheet by finite element simulation and obtained a basic concept which is important but can be ignored and reveal the factors which impact the transition zone of narrow sheet bending.

1) Strain neutral layer exists in narrow sheet bending process and it is a continuous layer. The strain neutral layer in deformation zone moves inwards equidistantly after bending but the strain neutral layer has non-equidistant inner shift in transition zone.

2) I did finite element simulation to narrow sheet bending process by using FEA ANSYS. The simulated results are the same as expected, i.e. The width of outer layer decreases while that of inner layer increases

after bending. In the smaller range of curvature radius, it has same displacement in width direction. The displacement in width direction gradually changes out of this range until it is the same as in non-deformation zone.

3) The position of transition zone is related to the curvature radius of narrow sheet. Under the same conditions, the transition zone is further from curvature center with longer curvature radius. However, the initial width of sheet does not have significant impact on position of transition zone. The range of transition zone is approximately same with different initial widths and curvature radius.

4) The distortion amounts of sheet are different on different sectional positions and different levels of transition zones. The distortion amounts are negative in the outer surface of the layer. And the distortion amount decreases gradually as getting close to the inner layer and distortion amount is zero when it is near the strain neutral layer. The distortion amount is positive afterwards and increases gradually. In the most inner surface, the positive distortion amount is maximum. When the sectional position is close to the deformation zone, the distortion amount of sheet is maximum. When the measured point moves towards non-deformation zone the distortion amount decreases gradually until zero.

5) The initial width and curvature radius have significant impact on the distortion amount of transition zone. The impact of initial width is the impact of the ratio of width and thickness which is b/t .

References

1. Abid M. EM, Zabit M. M, NIWIR , M. A, Hamel M. A, Bending of sheet metal (st37) using 90 degree to estimate blank dimensions, The International Journal Of Engineering and Information Technology. 2(2015).
2. Altan T, Erman Tekkaya A, Sheet metal forming processes and applications, ASM International. 2012.
3. Yibo H, Peiyuan C, Xingyuan Z, Discussion on the law of the inward movement of the neutral layer of the bending strain of the wide plate and the thinning of the plate thickness, China Metal Forming Equipment & Manufacturing Technology. 2016. (In Chinese)
4. Yibo H, Nengfeng L, Discussion on the inward movement of the neutral layer of wide plate bending based on the Finite Element Method, Technology Innovation and Application. 2021. (In Chinese)
5. Ling Yun Z, Bei Bei Z and Rui Z, Research on the shape distortions in plastic deformation area, Advanced Materials Research. 2012.
6. Ling Yun Z, Ren Chang H, Research on the hole shape distortions near the bending plastic deformation area, Applied Mechanics and Materials. 2013.
7. Xiaojing Z, Zhouxian B, Dongsheng L, Sheet Metal Forming Simulation Research Status [J], Plasticity Engineering. 2005,12 (9): 1-10.

© 2022 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

